

CONTENT AND LANGUAGE INTEGRATED LEARNING IN BILINGUAL

Madaminova Moxlaroyim Rustambek qizi

Student of NamSU, junior

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7039801>

Annotation: This article explores Content and Language Integrated Learning, benefits of CLIL coaching, what are the blessings of being bilingual, what are the advantages of CLIL method, how can instructors and colleges get the advantages of CLIL.

Keywords: Content, Language, Benefits of CLIL coaching approach If you're inquisitive about bilingual education, you've probably already encountered the time period CLIL — Content and Language Integrated Learning. The CLIL method includes studying approximately any other issue (the "content material") even as concurrently mastering the goal overseas language (the "incorporated studying"). Beyond knowledge what CLIL is, it's essential to apprehend why a CLIL method is beneficial. In this article, we'll study a number of the blessings of CLIL and the blessings of the use of this technique. Learn a way to placed CLIL into exercise to your institute with Bridge's Specialized Certificates in Content and Language Integrated Learning.

What are the blessings of being bilingual? Let's first lower back up simply a chunk and have a take a observe the wider discipline of bilingual education. Why is it vital? Studies the use of mind imaging strategies and different neurological checks have proven that there are real cognitive advantages from getting to know some other language, amongst them: Better communicate and interpersonal abilities. Bilingual human beings are greater unique of their phrase alternatives in each languages, and due to their focus of ability issues in communicate, they're extra touchy to capacity misunderstandings. Improved cognitive function. Bilingual human beings are extra bendy, and higher capable of alternate among responsibilities quickly. Memory is improved, and there's even proof that bilingualism can thrust back or as a minimum put off age-associated cognitive declines. Physical modifications to the mind. When bilingual and monolingual human beings are uncovered to a easy sound, research display that the blood float to the mind is better in bilingual humans. There is a correlation among how nicely you talk a 2d language, in addition to how younger you're while you study it, and the quantity of grey count in a few regions of the mind. In addition to the cognitive advantages, bilingual humans have get admission to to any other subculture and might discover greater artwork and literature in addition to journey and process possibilities.

What are the advantages of CLIL method? Within the sector of bilingual education, CLIL is extensively reputable as an powerful method. In fact, instructors discover that CLIL college students enhance their ratings withinside the language elegance and the problem location magnificence — or even their local language! Why does this happen? It's a end result of CLIL's interest to the goal language, the content material location, and additionally mastering capabilities themselves. Here are a number of the particular blessings. Learn approximately different famous ESL coaching methods.

A deeper knowledge of the goal language As college students analyze content material withinside the 2d language, they shape hyperlinks of their minds among their first language (or L1), the goal language (L2), and the content material. This fosters higher metalinguistic abilities: the capacity to mirror on language and meaning. They find out how languages paintings, in different words. Children who look at the policies of grammar of a 2nd language continuously locate themselves higher grammarians of their local language; every language may be studied thru the lens of the different.

Mastery of a concern While at the beginning development withinside the content material region might also additionally appear slower because the college students also are running of their L2, there's capacity for extra revision and deeper gaining knowledge of. Key ideas are strengthened withinside the language study room, and there are masses of possibilities for reviewing and recycling each statistics and language. A technology instructor may train how photosynthesis works even as introducing the important L2 vocabulary; later, withinside the language magnificence, the instructor ought to paintings on presentation talents, having college students provide an explanation for photosynthesis withinside the L2 thru a proper presentation, bringing in all of the useful language for scaffolding an oral presentation, operating with visible aids, managing target target market questions, and so on. Find out how study room shows issue into inquiry-primarily based totally studying. Improved social and crucial questioning abilities The identical blessings to communicative capacity that accrue to bilingual humans in widespread of direction come to college students in a CLIL software, and that they have greater possibilities to place the ones abilities into exercise as they circulate among the language study room and the problem study room. The language trainer would possibly train methods of agreeing, disagreeing, and soliciting for rationalization after which have college students practice the ones abilities to speak about a ancient occasion and its consequences. The records instructor would possibly then

arrange a debate on whether or not sure movements withinside the beyond have to or ought to now no longer had been taken, and college students will once more use their linguistic competencies.

A stronger, extra bendy mind Students in a CLIL software do greater than simply examine a language — they research withinside the language, so they're continuously the use of the language and improving. The language trainer explains the meanings of key vocabulary for chemistry, after which of their chemistry magnificence, college students can use the vocabulary in context as they conduct, discuss, and write up an experiment.

What styles of college students or faculty settings get the maximum gain from making use of the CLIL technique? CLIL works fine for topics with a cultural thing that scholars may be uncovered to along side the language and the content material — for example, social sciences, the arts, a few tough sciences, and a few vocational/technical trades. Schools that prefer institution paintings and tasks are especially properly-ideal to CLIL. As for college students, CLIL works superbly with a lot of ages, levels, and persona types. Many college students discover CLIL methodologies intrinsically interesting, that can upload the important thing factor of motivation to their research.

How can instructors and colleges get the advantages of CLIL? A CLIL software doesn't come collectively in a single day neither is it some thing one or instructors can perform alone. A hit CLIL software desires the knowledge and help of the administration, a shape that fosters communicate amongst content material and language instructors, and outreach to convey dad and mom in addition to college students on board. The Bridge Specialized Certificates in Content & Language Integrated Learning (CLIL) teach all stakeholders withinside the underpinning philosophy of this technique and the way to observe it institute-huge to provide tremendous getting to know results for college students. If you're new to coaching, you'll need to get preliminary education and qualification with a TEFL certificate. You can discover our on-line TEFL guides to get started!

What are a few demanding situations to the use of CLIL? Many of the demanding situations of adopting CLIL method come at the start of setting up the curriculum, so if all stakeholders are absolutely skilled in CLIL principle and programs and paintings collectively to put in force what they've learned, the organization can recover from those preliminary hurdles, and keeping the technique could be easier. As instructors and college students get used to new methods of running and mastering, they'll start to experience extra cushty and

notice measurable results, and with familiarity and alertness will come the rewards of CLIL. A success CLIL application can't most effective convey instantaneously advantages to college students of their language and difficulty place lessons however withinside the long time can enhance their cognitive abilities, lead them to higher communicators, and flip them into enthusiastic and a success lifelong learners. And the ones are advantages really well worth operating for.

References:

- [1] Coyle, D., Holmes, B., King, L. Towards an Integrated Curriculum – CLIL National Statement and Guidelines. London: The Languages Co., 2009.
- [2] Mehisto, P., Marsh, D., Frigols, M.J.. Uncovering CLIL. London: MacMillan, 2008.
- [3] Bandler, R., and Grinder, J. "Frogs Into Princes". Moab, UT: Real People Press, 1979. [4] Echevarria, J., Vogt, M.E. and Short, D. Making Content Comprehensible for English Learners. The SIOP Model. Boston u.a.: Pearson, 2006. [5] Echevarria, J., Vogt, M.E. and Short, D. Making Content Comprehensible for Elementary English Learners. The SIOP Model. Boston u.a.: Pearson, 2010. [6] Snow, M.A. "Instructional methodology in immersion foreign language education". In Padilla, A.M., Fairchild, H.H. and Valadez, CM. (Eds.). Foreign language education: Issues and strategies. Newbury Park, CA: Sage. , 1990, p. 161. [7] Ogle, D.M. K-W-L: A teaching model that develops active reading of expository text. Reading Teacher, 39, 1986, 564–570.

